

Future of Electronic Banking System in Bangladesh By the Year 2030

S M Basir, Aditya Mallik

BRAC Business School, Brac University, Bangladesh

basir.rafid1169@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

E-banking facilities and digital transactions have brought a revolution in the banking industry of Bangladesh. Online banking offers customers almost every service traditionally available through a local branch including deposits, transfers, and online bill payments. Almost all banks provide some type of internet banking, which is accessible through desktop and mobile apps. The future of banking is in electronic form. Regarding transaction costs and simplicity, it offers customers a wealth of advantages. However, it also presents fresh difficulties for national authorities in governing and overseeing the financial sector as well as in formulating and carrying out macroeconomic policies. There have been many new technologies introduced. Electronic banking can offer many advantages to users and new business possibilities to banks, but it also increases the hazards associated with traditional banking. Future technological innovation is anticipated and will soon be introduced. The potential for adding certain additional features to the electronic banking system is illustrated in the study article that follows.

Keywords: *E-banking, Digital currency, Blockchain Technology, NEO banks.*

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INTRODUCTION

In e-banking, funds are exchanged between financial institutions by electronic signals rather than through the exchange of cash, checks, or other negotiable instruments. To implement e-banking in the nation, it is crucial to have the right software, infrastructure, cyber security, and skilled manpower. This is because e-banking is expected to play a significant role in the national economy due to the expansion of global Information and Communication Technology (ICT) infrastructure and the internet. The traditional methods of doing tasks are no longer applicable in today's society, where the dynamic present is replacing the past and the challenging future is replacing both. Banks are expected to become physically disappeared by 2030. Leading banks may often sacrifice brand recognition to provide new financial services to customers using technology and information. The E-banking concept is a relatively

recent idea in the banking industry. Through the e-banking system, modern banks are exposed to technological advancements, which tend to make banking activities simpler and more convenient for both bankers and customers. The primary definition of e-banking, or electronic banking, is the use of computers, the internet, mobile devices, landlines, and ATM booths in virtually every industry.

Bangladesh is more likely than ever to use shadow banking techniques in the banking industry as it tries to position itself as a "Digital Bangladesh." E-banking is a subset of E-finance, which began as a component of E-Commerce. ATM services, Internet Banking, Call centers, SMS Banking, Telephone Banking, and Remittance are all examples of e-banking. Bangladeshis are becoming more interested in diversifying their sources of income and improving their standard of living. As a result, they must save as much time as possible, and e-banking is the best way to save time so that they can participate in their activities.

Thereby, the reasons for getting into electronic banking are quite obvious, such as It is time-consuming, easy, and affordable, it transforms the marketplace, it provides enhanced customer service, E-System vastly increases interactivity in the global economy and better communication across markets worldwide, and Flexibility is the underlying technical and philosophical ideology of the expansion of E-commerce. Bangladesh has a lot of potential in the e-banking sector. If the hazards are reduced and people are aware and optimistic about it, it will become much more popular in the future. Bangladesh, like other developed and developing countries throughout the world, should continue to practice e-banking for a smart and simple banking experience.

Objective

This paper aims to elaborate on the outcomes of our research about the future of electronic banking in Bangladesh by 2030. The main objective of this project is to enlighten about the possibilities of introducing virtual banking assistants & Robo advisors, the chances of decreasing the use of liquid cash & increasing the use of e-wallets, introducing blockchain technology for higher security, and chances of launching voice command system and possibilities of NEO banks entering the banking industry by 2030.

Scope

E-banking is becoming a worldwide phenomenon. Aside from developed countries, developing countries are having significant growth in e-banking. The Bangladesh Railway possesses a high-speed optical fiber network (18,00 km) parallel to the railway course that covers the majority of Bangladesh's vital areas. This optical fiber network has the potential to serve as the backbone network for e-banking in Bangladesh. For example, mobile phone companies in Bangladesh, such as Grameen Phone and Ranks ITT, use this optical fiber network to reach out to rural areas with their services. It's heartening to see that certain FCBs

and PCBs are already leveraging this optical fiber network for online transactions, ATMs, and POS services.

HYPOTHESES

The study on "**The Future of Electronic Banking System in Bangladesh by 2030**" is based on the following 5 hypotheses:

H1. The traditional banking system will introduce virtual banking assistants & Robo advisors for the convenience of their customers.

H2. Use of physical currency will decrease and the use of e-wallets & virtual currency will rise.

H3. The e-banking security system will be further strengthened using blockchain technology.

H4. A Voice command system will be added to the banking software.

H5. NEO banks or completely virtual banks will start their operations in Bangladesh by 2030

METHODOLOGY

This study has used secondary data. Document analysis is a methodical process of revising or appraising documents—both published and electronic (computer-based and Internet-transmitted) material. The current study especially searched websites, and articles related to digital banking on the future aspect using published or working papers of various recognized institutions, digital banking reports published by Bangladesh Bank, etc. However, some primary data were collected through discussion with some bank officers.

Findings and Outcomes

- **Launching Virtual Banking Assistant & Robo Advisor:**

Robo advisors use algorithms to create an automated asset distribution method (Chauhan, 2018). It is straightforward, easy to use, and requires low cost. These are digital financial advisors which provide financial advice to the clients based on the inputs received with moderate to minimal human intervention. It can manage the investment of the investors. Besides, using algorithms can make a prediction and understand the investor's preferences, risks, and goals. A set of psychographic and demographic questions based on gender, income,

liabilities, willingness to take on risk, and current asset allocation is asked and after analysis, it leads to a model portfolio and creates an investor profile. The profile is created focusing on the investor's goal and assessment of the risk profile of the client. Robo advisors judge the financial behavior of the client based on the financial transactions which include bank and credit card transactions, and investments, and later on, help the client by suggesting how the client should behave in the particular situation. AI constantly improves and thereby it learns about the client's spending patterns, current liabilities, and behavior in different scenarios and situations to make the most suitable, profitable, and appropriate investment decision for the client. Commercial banks in Bangladesh can provide users with hyper-personalized advice in real-time using machine learning Robo advisors. The AI-based Robo advisor is easy to access and free of human bias as it uses a mathematical algorithm to assess the investor. Robo advisors can take care of the entire financial planning of the client which includes a variety of services like tax-strategy schemes, rebalancing the portfolio, and retirement planning. It has a built mechanism that will help to keep track of the investor goals through timely reminders (Ganatra & Jain, 2021).

Virtual banking assistants like Chatbots would be more convenient for Bangladeshi clients. It will reduce the long queue in banks and save time, resources, and manpower costs. The traditional banking service is expected to be provided by virtual Chatbots online on the bank's official website or banking apps. The chatbot will answer all the questions as asked by the client through personal one-one conversations which will improve the customer experience. Personalized experience through chatbots is expected by around 63% of users in the world (Sanamandra, 2021). It will help by providing insights into a customer's finances like searching for past transactions, a weekly snapshot of spending, monitoring recurring charges, tracking trends of account balance, etc. Bangladesh Bank and other commercial banks may launch a virtual assistant like that of Bank of America's Erica which provides these services (Arefin, 2021). By giving a text command to the virtual assistant to transfer money to pay bills or canceling payments, check account balance, estimating future account balance based on the transactions and financial activities of the customer, summarize the transaction and prepare a monthly or weekly report, etc. will be done (Gran & Foreman, 2022). In the year 2030, all banks of Bangladesh are expected to have virtual assistants due to the technological advancement of AI which will enhance customer service, give users a personalized banking experience, cut down costs, mitigate risk better, improve work efficiency and reduce the workload of the employees.

- ***Rise of E-wallet & Digital Currency:***

E-wallets in Bangladesh started much earlier. However, due to security issues and new technologies, the use of such technologies took a long time to gain acceptance. However, this type of transaction system is gaining popularity nowadays. People can enjoy the benefits of Bkash, Nagad, Rocket, Upay, and many more e-banking wallets due to the development of Mobile Financial Services. At present, payment is being completed using the mentioned mobile financial services in various restaurants, shops, salons, medicine shops, etc. Also,

utility bills, hospital bills, and many other types of bills can be paid at home using these services. As a result, people's habit of carrying liquid cash is changing and the trend of using an e-wallet is increasing. Also, as the mobile service providers are affiliated with various banks, these e-wallets have the benefit of savings against fixed interest rates. The biggest advantage of these mobile service providers is that opening an account with them is very easy. Anyone can open an account and start transactions at home with only a National ID card (Opening a bKash account is simple).

With so many conveniences, the acceptance of e-wallets among consumers is increasing day by day. For instance, if we look at the current scenario of Bkash we can see that they currently have more than 2,00,000 agents and 50 million registered accounts (Company Profile, n.d.). This is a large number from the perspective of Bangladesh. This number is increasing every day. Talking about other mobile financial service providers they also have a large customer base. If we look around the number of online transactions using e-wallets has increased. Though the value of the physical currency will always be on the top the chances of using e-wallets for digital transactions going up crossing the use of physical currency is almost sure and according to our point of view, this incident will happen by 2030.

- ***Blockchain Technology for Better Security System:***

Using cryptographic algorithms and consensus mechanisms, blockchain security for the banking sector protects a decentralized network's risk management from cyber-attacks (Himanshi, 2022). Day by day online banking is gaining popularity in Bangladesh. However, the biggest question of the consumers is the issue of security. The biggest challenge of the moment in e-banking is the strong security system. Banking industry officials have already taken many steps to improve security systems. While depositing money in a branch of United Commercial Bank Limited, one of our research team members asked an employee there about the security system of e-banking. He said that many security systems have been introduced in Bangladesh and our country has a better security system for e-banking systems. But sometimes during international transactions, foreign hackers often access customer accounts and grab bank details & financial information. Experts are working hard to solve such problems.

When asked about this, a credit administration officer of City Bank said that the government and industry experts are trying to invent new strategies to make the security system of the online banking system stronger. Many developed countries around the world are already ensuring advanced security systems in their electronic banking sector using blockchain technology. The banking industry of Bangladesh is also going to bring this security system shortly. According to him, by 2030, the e-banking sector of Bangladesh will be able to launch a much stronger security system by introducing blockchain technology.

- ***Adding Voice Command System:***

Research indicates that voice payments were done by approximately 28% of customers, and keen interest was shown by 44% of indifferent customers in using voice assistants for everyday bank operations (Arefin, 2021). Voice-driven AI-based financial voice assistants will bring revolutionary changes to the banking industry of Bangladesh. Virtual voice assistants can make banking more efficient by providing all banking solutions as a whole. With the voice command, AI-based financial voice assistants will be able to identify the client through the automation of “Know your client” voice recognition. Moreover, people will be able to create bank accounts through financial voice assistants which will access the client’s personal information or take the information as voice input. The voice assistants will be able to understand both Bengali and English language to access any kind of information and carry out commands.

Quick transfer of money from peer to peer, making bill payments online, and transferring funds from one account to another can be done easily only just by a voice command to the AI-based voice assistant. It helps to keep track of customers’ spending by using voice commanding questions, “How much did I spend last month?”. Voice-Driven AI assistants will provide automated alerts if it sees any type of suspicious activity in the account such as possible fraud, duplicate charges, or large tips, and thereby the security of the client’s bank account is ensured. Using voice command, a client can access basic information about the bank account and its current status showing account balance, loans, and investments, and get account routing numbers. From the banking app of mobile, voice assistants will be able to lock and unlock credit and debit cards as well. To build trust, add value to the bank service, and help customers with what they want and need through the amazing experience, AI-based voice assistants will be initiated in the Bangladesh banking industry by 2030.

- ***Introducing NEO Banks:***

NEO banks are those banks that do not have physical branches like other traditional banks. These banks operate completely virtually. The chances of introducing these types of banks in every nation are very high now. According to some reports, Bangladesh is also going to launch this type of electronic banking service very soon. The launch of Neo Bank will usher in a groundbreaking development in the banking industry of Bangladesh. A committee was formed by the central bank of Bangladesh in 2021 to learn how such virtual banks are operating in other developed foreign countries and conduct research on the same. The report provided by the committee would be used to formulate new guidelines for establishing the NEO banks (Desk, 2022). Bangladesh Bank authority is currently drafting the necessary policies and legal guidelines for the establishment of such banks. Based on the preliminary report given by the committee, Bangladesh Bank will approve the operation of the bank in three stages after approving a new neo bank.

In the first phase, the bank will get permission only for retail businesses. In the second phase, SME banking will be approved and in the third phase, corporate lending and other corporate client deals will be approved. Such proposals are made to observe the movement and system of the work process. However, recently a new committee has been formed by senior experts, economists, and financial analysts which may lead to various changes in the current proposal. Overall, Bangladesh Bank is proceeding so much first to launch the virtual banks under the provision of the Bank Company Act. Already, mobile financial service provider Nagad & Bank Asia collaborated and applied for the license to launch the first NEO bank in the country (Insights, 2020). Many other banks and mobile financial service providers are also getting ready to enter the market of a completely virtual bank. According to the discussion, it's just a matter of time now to introduce this new electronic banking system in the Bangladeshi market. Moreover, In the budget session of the fiscal year 2022-23, Finance Minister A.H.M Mustafa Kamal MP mentioned the need for Neo Bank and said that if the digital bank is established, the economy will increase further. Besides, the country's IT sector will expand and the number of jobs will increase. It can be assured from his statement that the establishment of Neo Bank is very close.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The new features and technologies introduced in the E-banking sector now have made life so much easier. The launch of the above-mentioned features will be a blessing for the users of Bangladesh. Even though some nations have made significant progress in modifying their banking and supervisory laws, ongoing scrutiny and adjustments will be necessary as e-banking expands. More harmonization and coordination, in particular, still need to be established at the global level. Additionally, a higher sensitivity to the administration of economic policy is created by the potential ease with which capital may be transferred between banks and across borders in an electronic environment. Policymakers need a strong intellectual framework to comprehend how e-banking affects the way economic policy is conducted.

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